

Review

Influence of Social Media Marketing on Performance of Small And Medium-Sized Enterprises in an economy: Literature Review

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Abstract: The main aim of the research was to investigate how Social Media Marketing impacts the performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. This research utilized a literature review search by consulting academic databases; Google scholars, Research Gate, Scopus, among others to gather pertinent information regarding the subject. The research indicated that using Facebook marketing had increased recognition of the business' services and products, facilitated customer association with the brand, and often allowed businesses to understand societal needs. The rise of close customer relationships with businesses has been supported by Facebook as it has become the primary platform for businesses to interact with both current and potential customers. The research showed that Instagram allowed for creative engagement with customers through entertaining and informative posts, leading to adjustments in marketing strategies to reach a wider audience. WhatsApp marketing was found to be user-friendly, promoting interaction between customers and businesses at a lower cost, and customers could easily navigate the business catalog. Utilizing WhatsApp Business marketing allowed businesses to easily adjust their brand based on customer feedback and also facilitated direct communication with customers. The research findings show that Facebook made it easy for businesses to reach their target market, attracting more customers and helping them gain new clients.

Keywords: Social media, Performance, small and medium size enterprise

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Introduction

The business landscape is expanding quickly, with challenges on the rise such as competition from new companies, heightened rivalry from established firms, and strong bargaining power from buyers (Mirzaei, Ranganathan, Kearns, Airehrour & Etemaddar, 2019). This present market situation has created many risks and opportunities in equal proportions (Hargreaves, 2018). Additionally, it has led to a highly competitive business climate. Multiple businesses and

firms have been inspired to adjust their strategies in order to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors and maintain their market support from customers, clients, and supply chains. Several strategies used by companies to stay competitive include forming strategic partnerships, merging with other companies, reducing costs, offering unique products, and providing differentiated services (Antelo & Peon, 2019). With the recent trend of technological progress, social media has become a crucial tool for entrepreneurs.

Social media is the way people share and receive information with each other through the use of the internet (Ismail, Nguyen & Melewar, 2018). Social media has made it easier and quicker for people to connect, resulting in increased interaction, collaboration, and participation among individuals. Several small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that have started using social media have seen an increase in customer awareness and accessibility. The acknowledgment, prevalence, and utilization of social media have significantly increased in the last decade in developed and developing countries alike (Akram & Kumar, 2017).

This trend is expected to continue growing in the upcoming years. Businesses and enterprises are eager to use internet applications for marketing, aiming to keep current customers, attract new ones, increase sales, and maximize profits. Amid intense competition in the market, many small and medium-sized businesses are choosing to embrace digital marketing to achieve their marketing and sales objectives (Chinakidzwa & Phiri, 2020). Based on Kaplan & Haenlein (2010), social media, a component of internet communication technology, are internet-based applications that are built on the principles and technology of Web 2.0, enabling users to create and share content. Some of the platforms mentioned are Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, and LinkedIn. The rise of social media has resulted in companies implementing marketing strategies linking electronic word of mouth that impacts and shapes customer buying decisions (Xie et al., 2016).

Social media platforms allow customers to access information on products and brands based on other customers' experiences and recommendations (Chen et al., 2011; Chanthinok et al., 2015). Social media also have a significant impact on building trust and forming connections with clients, vendors, and potential collaborators. Firms can boost business values and improve brand values by earning trust and fostering relationships, as suggested by Kumar et al. (2013), Hudson et al. (2016), and Zhang et al. (2017). E-commerce and social media technology play a crucial role in the operation and success of many businesses in today's world (Grewal, Motyka & Levy, 2018). A key factor for this is that platforms such as Twitter and Facebook have created a sense of intimacy and connection through online communication (Camil, 2017). Social media is essential for businesses of all types as it allows them to interact with consumers, listen to their feedback, and learn from them quickly and cost-effectively compared to traditional communication methods (Akram & Kumar, 2017).

According to Hofacker, Golgeci, Pilai, and Gligor (2020), individuals and companies are adopting social media platforms available on networks to share ideas and information. Many popular social media platforms like Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, and Snap Chat have experienced significant growth, allowing businesses to reach their target audience online (Bahadur, 2021). Currently, companies have their own social media profiles and encourage individuals to follow and like their product pages. They continuously update their pages to share information. Roughly 90 percent of Americans use the internet and social media, and this figure continues to grow every day. Due to the convenience of social media platforms on mobile devices, many businesses, including small and medium-sized enterprises, find it easier to communicate through these platforms. Small and medium-sized businesses also tend to have adaptable decision-making systems that make it easier to implement non-traditional strategies such as social media marketing.

According to Blassnig, Ernst, Engesser and Esser (2019), social media marketing in the United States had experienced significant growth over the past decade and was expected to continue expanding in the next ten years. Blassnig et al. (2019) conducted their research from a U.S. standpoint. A study by Kiss, Koncz, Nagyne, Varro, Nemeth and Ruszkai (2019) investigated the efficiency of social media marketing in Hungary. The research found that marketing strategies

such as direct contact interactions and sharing branded content publicly are highly effective techniques. Nonetheless, his research did not accurately assess how each method impacted the performance of small and medium enterprises. Silva, Duarte, and Almeida (2020) conducted research aiming to develop methods for evaluating the return on investment of a company through social media marketing strategies. The study's results indicated that evaluating the effectiveness of social media marketing campaigns was best done through immediate financial performance due to its unique approach. Silva et al. (2020) suggested that focusing on marketing performance is crucial as social media helps boost brand loyalty and customer motivation. The research, nonetheless, did not implement the model and use it to examine the effects of various social media marketing campaigns on businesses. Amoah and Jibril (2021) conducted research on the use of social media for promoting growth of small and medium-sized businesses in Ghana. Amoah and Jibril (2021) distributed 800 surveys and discovered that utilizing social media significantly impacts a company's financial performance and market share, making it a crucial tool for influencing promotional and marketing strategies in the consumer market. The research proposed additional studies in different fields due to Amoah and Jibril concentrating on the financial sector. The research emphasized the importance of businesses investing in digital marketing and using it effectively for a competitive advantage in the future, ensuring the company's survival and eventual expansion. Arjmand (2020) has demonstrated this information. When executed correctly, social media marketing can enhance recognition and motivate the market to buy, recognize, and repeatedly purchase the products and services being promoted online, ultimately building brand loyalty. Additional scholars such as Hobson (2017) and Deges (2018) found that as technology progresses and online platforms become more popular, individuals have taken advantage of using their mobile devices and gadgets to share information on social media networks. As a result, social media has become a strong marketing tool for reaching the public. The idea of social media is quite unclear. According to Wang, Rod, and Deng (2017), social media is supported by various values such as the involvement of interested individuals, transparency in sharing information and providing feedback, engagement based on community, continuous discussion on specific topics, and the connection between individuals and organizations. According to Hofacker, Golgeci, Pilai and Gligor (2020), individuals and groups are adopting social media platforms available on the internet to communicate thoughts and details.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Tajvidi and Karami (2017) conducted research in Wales to examine how social media impacts the hotel industry performance, revealing a direct correlation between hotel performance and social media usage. In their study, Ye, Yu, Zheng, and Zheng (2021) researched how social media application impacts a company's performance and capabilities. They discovered that social media can enhance a company's adaptability and agility, while time-based performance should be carefully monitored in the face of a volatile external business environment. Chen and Lin (2019) conducted research to explore the impact of social media marketing on satisfaction through perceived value, social identification, and satisfaction. The findings showed that social media marketing activities, perceived value, and social identification have an indirect impact on satisfaction, while perceived value and social identification directly influence satisfaction, leading to continuance intention, purchase intention, and participation intention. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of social media marketing on the success of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in an economy, which represents a significant portion of the SMEs operating in an economy. The majority of past studies on social media usage centered on big companies. This study aimed to address the lack of knowledge regarding the impact of social media marketing on small and medium-sized businesses in an economy. It also aimed to provide recommendations on how these businesses can improve their operations through cost-effective marketing on Facebook, WhatsApp, and Instagram.

2. Literature Review

The review was based on three applications as a representative of social media and how they influenced marketing of products within the small and medium sized enterprises and three areas include; Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp.

2.1 Facebook Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

A company could utilize the various points of engagement on social media to achieve a specific objective. Every point of contact must be used effectively in order to achieve a business's goal of increasing online sales to an e-commerce site. Salloum, Al-Emran, Monem and Shalaan (2017) suggested that the use of "Like" ads on Facebook can increase fan page followers among the desired audience. The fact that Facebook allows users who are at least thirteen years old is a key factor in why it has a high number of active users. Chugh and Ruhi (2018) stated that after Facebook was introduced in 2004, it now provides a range of ways to engage and connect with potential customers. Galati, Crescimanno, Fagnani and Tinervia (2017) stated that Facebook had more than 750 million active users in 2011, and the amount rose to 1.45 billion active users by mid-2015. Facebook holds the top position as the most utilized social media platform worldwide. Facebook is capable of creating a webpage that functions as an extension of a store to interact with customers and clients. The page also enables the sharing of content, advertising of products, services, brands, and deals, while also drawing in virtual customers. Facebook can also be used for promoting products and sharing links to industry or business blog posts with online consumers (Chugh & Ruhi, 2018). Recent data shows that Facebook has generated more than five billion US dollars in revenue from advertising (Iqbal, 2021). Facebook recently bought stakes in Vine, Instagram, and Snap Chat, enhancing its reach and impact on society, resulting in a greater influence on businesses and organizations.

2.1.1 Brand Awareness Increase

The main needs for linking brands with their user community include advocacy, information, identity, affiliation, and conversation (Antonov, 2021). However, marketers must comprehend the issues of online users and the societal impacts before engaging in marketing activities. To determine people's priorities, it is important to take into account their moral beliefs and essential needs. Therefore, it is important for the growth of the market to use social media platforms such as Facebook as a crucial marketing tool that aligns with societal ethics. Bilgin (2018) examined the current state of Facebook marketing, which helped companies grow and increase brand visibility. Melghagh and Ouahi (2021) stated that Facebook allowed virtual consumer communities to come together around brands, such as Jeep and Nutella, establishing a real marketing space with internet-based exchanges and engagements.

2.1.2 Decisions of Purchasing Power

The trend of using social media for making buying choices has remained steady in recent times. Warsame, Mohammed, Elamir, and Aziz (2021) carried out research to explore how behavioral attitudes impact Facebook, the most widely used social media platform among millennials in Somalia. They also assessed if different demographic factors and usage influenced the perceptions of purchase and intention-to-purchase. The research utilized quantitative methods through a survey of over three thousand participants in South Africa, who self-administered a questionnaire. Sanne and Wiese (2018) found that advertising on Facebook positively influenced the purchasing behaviors and intentions of South African millennials. The way Facebook is used and how often profiles are updated also resulted in a more positive view of advertising on the platform. The study took place in South Africa, while countries such as Tanzania require more research to identify if they also exhibit similar favorable attitudes towards purchasing and intention-to-purchase decisions through the use of Facebook.

In Rana's (2016) research, it was found that consumers typically pay less attention to a brand's image when making purchasing choices, despite the fact that marketers dedicate many hours to developing it. The study also showed that people are more affected by the opinions and recommendations of friends on Facebook, which have a significant impact on their buying decisions. According to Fink, Koller, Gartner, Floh, and Harms (2020), celebrity endorsements were the least effective factor in Facebook marketing, showing that consumers were more influenced by the opinions of their friends and family. This required additional collaborative efforts from the companies, advertisers, and stakeholders. Advertisers to expand their brand values and grow their client roster. Marketers should embrace both work and relationship marketing tactics when dealing with clients to enhance interaction and communication for positive outcomes. Moreover, it is important to focus on specific social groups and influential individuals in order to attract more customers

to the service or product being marketed (Zhou, McCormick, Blazquez & Barnes, 2019). With the rise in internet users, technology firms have created numerous methods to incorporate the digital world into shopping, leading to expected significant growth in online retail. The abbreviated customer experience simplifies the process for consumers by allowing them to quickly buy the product in just one minute. According to a Deloitte study, twenty-nine percent of individuals who use social media are more inclined to make a purchase on the same day through social media channels. This means that when they spot the product, they just need to click on it in order to buy it. Additionally, individuals who are impacted by social media are more inclined to make purchases online, as stated by Voramontri & Klieb in 2019. Additionally, it was mentioned that the impact of social proof and influencers greatly affects consumer buying choices when it comes to making online purchases through social media platforms. Whenever someone shares a post or tweet about a fantastic cafe or a hair product that worked wonders for them, their followers on social media take notice and might decide to give the item a try. The same is true for complaints and negative viewpoints.

2.1.3 Increase Customer Relationship

Facebook is used to nurture customer connections within the hospitality industry. The primary aim of the study was to assess how Facebook affects the factors that drive relationships and the benefits that customers perceive from Pite Havsbad. Moller and Omojola (2018) investigated how various Facebook interactions, relational advantages, and relationship incentives are interconnected. The survey form on the Facebook page of Pite Havsbad was conducted by the researcher using quantitative data. The researcher collected data from 256 participants and utilized SPSS to analyze the data through Cronbach's alphas test, multiple regression, and Pearson correlation analysis to examine the expected relationships between the two variables. The research results revealed that interactions on Facebook influenced both relational benefits and relationship drivers, despite having a lesser impact on relational benefits. However, the relationship drivers have a significant impact on the relational benefits. In general, the study participants highly appreciated the Facebook activities of Pite Harshad, indicating that all of these activities have the potential to strengthen relationships with clients. Through conducting this study, the researcher indicates that it helped Pite Havsbad in laying the groundwork for developing a social customer relationship management strategy that could be used for fostering relationships with their Facebook followers in the future. Brand pages on social media are now seen as an important tool for building relationships and are becoming increasingly popular as a key marketing strategy in various industries. In his research, De Silva (2020) examined a group of three hundred college students who use Facebook. The examination of the results showed that customer interactions with Facebook Brand Pages in fashion/apparel and restaurants/hotels were greatly affected by client motivation, social interaction, rewards, information, and personal identity. The connection between customer engagement and entertainment motivation was found to be not important. Furthermore, there was a significant positive correlation between customer engagement and commitment and trust towards Facebook Brand Page. It stressed the importance of Facebook Brand Pages as an effective marketing tool for establishing connections with consumers and clients. De Silva (2020) recommended that marketers first ascertain the expectations of experts from Facebook Fan Pages before engaging them on the platform to enhance their relationship with the page.

2.1.4 Reaching Wider Range of Customers

Facebook Commerce boosts the productivity of small and medium-sized businesses. Alraja, Khan, Khashab, and Aldaas (2020) set out to determine the factors influencing the uptake of Facebook commerce, specifically focusing on Facebook ads for SMEs and their impact on enhancing the organizational performance of these small and medium-sized enterprises. The researcher primarily focused on organizational performance across three aspects: flexibility, responsiveness, and efficiency. The investigation utilized a combination of descriptive research design and quantitative research approach. Data was gathered from different small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in Dhofar and Muscat regions of Oman. There was a total of three hundred and forty-two questionnaires. The results of the study showed that factors like user-friendliness, engagement, targeting specific demographics, and brand recognition accounted for twenty percent of the differences in Facebook ad performance as the predictor variable. Statistical analysis

revealed that Facebook ads had a notable impact on the efficiency, flexibility, and responsiveness of small and medium-sized businesses, with regression coefficients of 0.51, 0.66, and 0.74, respectively. This explains 44% of the efficiency variance, 26% of the flexibility variance, and 55% of the responsiveness variance.

2.2 Instagram Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises

Recent technological advancements have revolutionized the conventional methods of marketing according to Boyd & Holton (2018). Instagram leads the way in helping companies reach their target customer groups through visual content. Instagram is a widely used social media platform around the world (Harun & Tajudeen, 2020). The conventional methods of marketing, including print and electronic media, along with internet marketing, are used to attract visitors to companies and their websites. When search engine processes advance, website owners must constantly stay alert to update their sites with up-to-date and pertinent information to avoid losing value in search results (Helal, Ozuem & Lancaster, 2018). Presently, Instagram and other social media platforms are being viewed as marketing platforms. Instagram is widely utilized across the globe as a social media platform, and it has a significant impact on revolutionizing the online shopping industry (Pabalkar & Negi, 2020). Forty-four percent of Instagram users use the platform to explore and find new brands, while fifty-three percent use it to follow their favorite brands (Varma, Dhakane & Pawar, 2020). Influencers have a crucial role to play, along with their large following. Collaborating with influencers is increasingly common for brands, as it proves to be a lucrative strategy due to the accessibility of connecting with Instagram audiences as opposed to celebrities.

2.2.1 Customer Engagements

Before introducing a new product or service, an individual wants to understand how the business is viewed by others (Ahmad, & Bakar, 2018). Engaging with customers and prospects on Instagram allows you to ask their favorite colors or desired features. Therefore, one can involve customers in valuable market research by asking for their opinions. Once a business or organization has familiarized themselves with the ideas and put them into action, they can potentially expand their customer base (Varma et al., 2020). Wahid and Wadud (2020) emphasized that anyone who provides value to customers of the company can engage in activities such as sharing, commenting, and liking information and entertainment content. By actively involving customers, businesses can gather more feedback, including both positive remarks and criticisms (Kumar, Rajan, Gupta & Pozza, 2019). Therefore, it is important for small and medium enterprises to involve their clients by providing different opportunities for interaction and entertainment, enabling them to give feedback on how the company operates.

2.2.2 Marketing Strategies Modification

Businesses are always adjusting their marketing strategies by analyzing information they receive about their competitors on social media networks. Observing rivals can help determine their marketing efforts based on their strengths and weaknesses (Saura, Palacios-Marques & Iturricha-Fernandez, 2021). The gathered data can help improve activities like competitions, promotions, and social media initiatives by tailoring content that will engage followers effectively. People prefer to buy from companies that are reputable and appear to be completely open about their marketing efforts. The consumer awareness has significantly impeded the customer acquisition process (Kumar et al., 2019). Instagram is proving to be useful in reshaping people's views and judgments towards businesses. Through providing messages that are open, helpful, and transparent, social audiences can see that a business truly values both potential and existing customers. One can demonstrate resourcefulness by providing information such as tips, advice, or answers related to a specific industry (Grewal et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Influence Purchasing Decisions

Pabalkar and Negi (2020) conducted research to explore the impact of Instagram influencers and Instagram on purchase decisions within the Indian fashion sector. Pabalkar & Negi (2020) employed an exploratory research method and set up a formal survey as a result. The research showed that blogs and posts greatly impact the behavior of young

individuals, which can be both harmful and beneficial for businesses. The researchers found that satisfied consumers used forums to share feedback about their experience with the services and products. The company will gain a significant insight on their knowledge and necessary changes through blog posts and forum feedback. Additionally, most businesses in the fashion and apparel industry recognize the influence blogs can have on their target consumers and view them as a valuable method for distributing and selling their products. The research had various restrictions as it solely examined female participants and was limited to the fashion sector in India. However, the study concentrated primarily on Instagram influencers, while the present study is centered on the impact of social media on small and medium-sized businesses. This research aims to close this gap by investigating the influence of Instagram on creating brand loyalty for small and medium-sized enterprises.

2.2.4 E-commerce Influence

Aziz, Rashid and Adnan (2021) conducted research to investigate how mothers utilized E-commerce platforms and Instagram during the Covid-19 Pandemic. In 2021, Aziz and colleagues observed that Instagram had entered the realm of e-commerce, quickly establishing itself as a crucial tool for marketing. The use of Instagram, especially in the field of e-commerce, has grown significantly. The research was conducted in Malaysia to understand the factors that influenced the utilization of Instagram as a shopping tool by mothers amidst the Covid-19 pandemic. Aziz et al. (2021) employed a combination of phenomenology and qualitative methods in their research. The research showed that various elements influenced how Instagram was used, the diverse reasons for using it, and the advantages for consumers. The research utilized a group of twenty individuals and found that efficiency in terms of time and cost played a significant role in impacting the online shopping behavior through social media among the participants. The research showed that consumers are able to easily compare prices using Instagram without any pressure.

2.3. WhatsApp Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises

WhatsApp is a messaging app that can help businesses have a greater impact on customer satisfaction (Presti, Maggiore, Marino & Resciniti, 2021). Brands can increase their reach and improve the effectiveness of their message delivery. Nevertheless, companies and businesses have enhanced the safe manner of communicating with their clients while also boosting interactions. Additionally, companies can achieve several key business goals by utilizing the messaging tool. WhatsApp Business was introduced in January 2018, according to Chamat (2020). At first, WhatsApp was restricted to several countries and was exclusively on Android systems. The app has now been enhanced to be compatible with additional mobile platforms such as iOS, and its accessibility has been extended to cover more countries, including Switzerland. WhatsApp Business introduces a new approach to customer-business interactions that stresses the importance of rapid messaging for effective communication. WhatsApp Business has gained popularity for its proven advantages in improving market strategies and customer service for companies and organizations.

2.3.1 User Friendly

Small businesses in India have faced challenges when using online platforms. Bhat (2021) conducted a study aiming to uncover the reasons behind the difficulties faced by SMEs when using social media. The researcher observed the economic growth in India, while individuals have realized the opportunities available for entrepreneurship. The result is a significant rise in small and medium-sized enterprises nationwide, necessitating a platform for their representation. WhatsApp Business is being adopted by numerous small sellers in India (Bala & Verma, 2018). According to Buteau (2021), in order to comprehend the impact of WhatsApp Business on small businesses, it was necessary to first understand the obstacles and challenges faced by entrepreneurs in this sector.

Advertising on Facebook and WhatsApp is crucial for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Negedu and Isik (2020) employed the case study of the Abuja Municipal Area Council. The collected data was examined by the researchers with the help of SPSS software. Initially, the survey data was given to four hundred and thirty-eight individuals. The purpose of the survey was to gather opinions on the impact and benefits of social media advertising for

businesses within the local council. The outcomes of the survey were showcased through bar graphs, tables showing frequencies, and histograms. The research showed that social media ads positively impacted business growth in Nigeria, with potential for improving business operations if suggested changes were implemented and enhancements were made. The researchers also suggested a list of suggestions for their research, one of which was the importance of reducing online transaction fees for small businesses, particularly those that are just starting out. The primary focus of the study was on smaller businesses, while this study includes both small and medium-sized businesses, so the results of Negedu and Isik's (2020) study may not directly apply to this research situation. Alhameli, Hamid, Alwaini, and Asad (2020) conducted research to investigate how social media tools affect the performance of small and medium businesses. The case study of the United Arab Emirates was utilized. The primary aim of the research was to assess if social media is more suitable for evaluating SMEs' performance in the United Arab Emirates. The researcher used a quantitative approach, distributing 350 questionnaires, with 263 returned and 245 used for analysis. The results showed that email, Twitter, and WhatsApp had a significant and positive impact on the performance of small and medium-sized businesses.

2.3.2 Low Costs of Operations

Social media has played a role in the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in Lagos and Onitsha, Nigeria. Morah and Omojola (2018) conducted an evaluation of their connection. They utilized a descriptive survey design to analyze three hundred small and medium-sized businesses in the two cities through the use of a questionnaire. The results showed that a higher use of WhatsApp resulted in increased market access and enhanced customer relationships as it was a more cost-effective way to communicate with clients. The results of the research greatly influenced the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises. Although Facebook and WhatsApp have the potential to increase visibility, many business owners are unaware of them. Therefore, it is necessary to educate them about using social media as part of their economic growth strategy.

2.3.3 Platform of Sustainable Business

WhatsApp Messenger was first created by Jan Koum and Brian Acton in order to enhance and accelerate communication through message sharing. Afful and Akrong (2020) point out that WhatsApp enables users to communicate with family and friends by utilizing internet connection. It also helps to form groups, share videos, pictures, and audio messages. At present, WhatsApp Messenger is present and contributes to fostering economic development, particularly in Africa. Research has shown that WhatsApp has become one of the most popular instant messaging apps in recent times (Endeley, 2018). Afful and Akrong (2020) mentioned in their research that WhatsApp is not only useful for online advertising but also for various other promotional activities, all of which have a positive impact on business operations. Morah and Omojola (2018) agree with Afful and Akrong's findings, suggesting that social media platforms can be used as a cost-effective alternative to traditional marketing strategies for SMEs to improve brand recognition and streamline management. This means that small and medium-sized businesses greatly profit from using social media for their business, especially WhatsApp. To sum up, social media plays a major role in shaping business entities by improving communication for better customer relationships.

The organization's dynamic capabilities typically demonstrate how it updates its response competencies in the constantly changing business environment. In 2019, Tolani, Owoseni, and Twinomurinzi conducted research to investigate how mobile apps impact small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria. The research utilized retrodiction and content analysis to assess sixteen SMEs in five Nigerian states through their dynamic capabilities of small and medium-sized enterprises. As a result, it was discovered that in Nigeria, mobile apps such as WhatsApp are utilized for executing business tasks by leveraging their ability to sense changes effectively.

The research also found that although there is government support available for small businesses nationwide, the programs are often difficult to access and lack necessary mobile application features. Thus, Tolani et al. (2019) suggested the importance of creating a mobile app tailored for small and medium-sized enterprises in developing countries. Recently, WhatsApp enabled businesses to start private conversations with their customers through their direct messaging platform. Zarouali, Brosius, Helberger and De Vreese (2021) utilized information from a nationwide research study and found a positive relationship between the trust in popular brands for messaging and perceived socialness, perceived security, and perceived privacy of WhatsApp. As a result, trust in the brand had a positive impact on customers' willingness to share their information with WhatsApp. Additionally, the research also indicated that WhatsApp has the potential to serve as a valuable tool for engaging with both clients and customers in a strategic manner. By setting up a business account on WhatsApp, companies can utilize the app's views on privacy, social connections, and security to increase their brand trust with specific customers, ultimately encouraging them to share more information about the brand (AlArfaj & Solaiman, 2019). Zarouali and colleagues (2021) suggested in their research that businesses should improve their marketing strategy by establishing business profiles on WhatsApp. This way, they can offer customers the opportunity to engage with the brand through direct messaging.

3. Research Methodology

The study employed qualitative research where the data were collected through literature review and compiled together to address the research questions. The data were mainly collected from Google Scholar and research gates which were in line with the research objectives. Data were then presented in themes according to the research questions.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Facebook Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises.

The research revealed that the businesses' services and products saw increased brand awareness due to Facebook marketing efforts. This result is consistent with Alraja et al.'s (2020) research, which focused on determining the factors influencing the adoption of Facebook commerce, specifically the impact of Facebook ads on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and their organizational performance. Their findings showed that ease of use, interaction, demographic targeting, and brand awareness explained twenty percent of the variability in Facebook ad effectiveness as the independent variable.

The research showed that Facebook assisted consumers in connecting with the brand of the businesses' product. The findings align with Antonov (2021) who suggests that key elements for linking brands with their user community include advocacy, information, identity, affiliation, and conversation. Bilgin (2018) examined the current Facebook marketing strategies that helped businesses grow and build brand awareness. As per Melghagh and Ouahi (2021), Facebook allowed the creation of virtual consumer communities to promote brands such as Jeep and products like Nutella, establishing a real marketing space via online transactions and interactions. The research indicated that Facebook typically allowed business owners and managers to uncover the needs of society. This result aligns with the findings of Moller and Omojola (2018) on the correlation between various Facebook activities, relational advantages, and relationship motivators in Pite Havsbad, Sweden. The results indicated that interactions on Facebook influenced both relationship advantages and factors driving relationships, despite having a lesser impact on relationship benefits. The relationship drivers greatly affect the relational advantages.

The research showed that customers viewed different Facebook business pages before buying. The findings align with De Silva (2020) who believes that brand pages on social media are becoming more popular as a crucial marketing tactic in various industries to build relationships. In his research, he utilized a group of 300 Facebook users who were undergraduates. The study showed that customer interactions on Facebook Brand Pages in fashion/apparel and restaurants/hotels were greatly affected by client motivation, social interaction, rewards, information, and personal identity.

The research indicated that sales are increased by discounts and promotions featured on the company's Facebook page. The findings align with Chugh and Ruhi's (2018) assertion that Facebook can be utilized to establish a webpage functioning as an extension of an online store for engaging with customers and clients. The page enables the distribution of content, promotion of products, services, brands, and offers, and attracts online shoppers. Facebook can also be used for promoting products and sharing blog posts related to the industry or business with online consumers.

The research showed that Facebook had helped to enhance strong customer connections with the company. This research finding aligns with De Silva's (2020) assertion that different relationship principles guided different types of Facebook Brand Pages. Therefore, the strength of connections between customer engagement and customer satisfaction, as well as the connections between outcomes of Facebook Brand Page and customer engagement, relied on the specific type of Facebook Brand Pages. Moreover, customer engagement was found to act as an intermediary in the connections between trust in Facebook Brand Pages and motives (social interaction, personal identity, and information compensation). The examination found that Facebook had turned into the primary platform for communication between the company and its current and potential customers. The findings align with Alraja et al. (2020)'s research on the factors influencing the adoption of Facebook commerce, focusing on the impact of Facebook ads on SMEs' organizational performance. The study concluded that ease of use, interaction, demographic targeting, and brand awareness accounted for 20% of the variance in Facebook ad effectiveness. Storozhenko (2019) determined that interactive social media platforms offered numerous improved prospects for small and medium enterprises, starting with saving money that would have been spent on visiting a physical store. However, through interactive social media, individuals can manage their businesses or enterprise from any location.

4.2 WhatsApp Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

The research demonstrated that employing WhatsApp for marketing purposes was effortless and facilitated communication between customers and businesses. The findings align with Zarouali et al. (2021) who suggest that WhatsApp enables companies to start private chats with customers through their direct messaging system, potentially becoming a crucial strategic tool for engaging with clients. AlArfaj and Solaiman (2019) suggest that by creating a business account on WhatsApp, brands can leverage the app's views on privacy, social interaction, and security to build trust with their target consumers, ultimately increasing their willingness to share brand-related information. The research showed that using WhatsApp for marketing was more cost-effective and the majority of customers could quickly learn how to access the product catalog. The results of the study align with Morah and Omojola's (2018) research, which showed that using WhatsApp resulted in greater market access and better customer relationships due to its cost-effective nature and ease of communication with clients. In their study, Wisnalmawati et al. (2021) found that WhatsApp Business was beneficial for businesses due to its cost-free nature, security assurances, comprehensive small business descriptions, seamless payment integration, various messaging choices, customer service, and business analytics availability. The research showed that using WhatsApp for marketing made it convenient for customers to buy what they desired. This study's findings support Voramontri and Klieb's (2019) assertion that individuals who are influenced by social media are more inclined to make online purchases.

Kumar et al. (2019) believe that consumers prefer buying from companies with established credibility and transparent advertising practices. The customer acquisition process has significantly decreased due to consumer awareness. Research indicated that communication for clarification purposes could be easily initiated between clients and businesses. The result aligns with Varma et al. (2020) who suggest that by interacting with customers and potential customers on Instagram, individuals can inquire about their favorite colors or desired features. Therefore, one can involve customers in valuable market research by asking for their opinions. Grewal et al. (2020) suggest that social audiences perceive a business enterprise as caring about both potential and existing clients when it provides open,

helpful, and transparent messages. One can establish themselves as knowledgeable by offering guidance, suggestions, or solutions to questions related to a specific field. The research showed that utilizing WhatsApp Business marketing allowed businesses to effortlessly adjust their business brand based on customer feedback. The research indicated that the utilization of WhatsApp for marketing had boosted customer purchasing choices in businesses. The findings support the views of Negedu and Isik (2020), who believe that Facebook and WhatsApp advertising are highly crucial for small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) start-ups in Nigeria. Their research showed that social media ads greatly impacted the growth of businesses in Nigeria and could also improve business operations in the country. Alhameli et al. (2020) conducted research to determine how social media tools affect the performance of small and medium businesses.

4.3 Instagram Marketing and Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

The research indicated that businesses could easily interact with clients by using Instagram to send out advertisements and samples. This result is consistent with Kumar et al.'s (2019) assertion that people prefer buying from companies that have established credibility and appear completely transparent in their advertising efforts. The consumer awareness has significantly slowed down the customer acquisition process. Storozhenko (2019) highlights the lack of balance and ease. The discrepancy between what is given and the pressure of advertising and product promotions. The research showed that Instagram facilitated creative engagement with customers by sharing entertaining and informative posts. This study aligns with Pabalkar and Negi (2020) in suggesting that many businesses utilize social media platforms such as Instagram to enhance consumer engagement by gathering feedback and reviews, leading to increased connection with the organization. Therefore, Instagram provides a platform for both small and big businesses to allow their customers to provide feedback on different services and products through their existing Instagram pages.

The research demonstrated that businesses were able to adapt their marketing techniques to reach a wider audience and customer base through Instagram. The study findings support Saura et al.'s (2021) assertion that companies are constantly adjusting their marketing tactics based on data obtained from their competitors on social media platforms. By observing rivals, their strengths and weaknesses can show how much they are putting into marketing. Instagram is proving to be very useful by transforming people's views on businesses and changing their perceptions. The research showed that businesses were able to openly communicate and share messages through Instagram. Instagram is proving useful by changing people's views and attitudes towards businesses. Social media users have discovered that being honest, open, and transparent in their messages can be beneficial for their business. The research demonstrated that Instagram typically results in increased creativity in marketing and personal selling by catering to customer demands. This study's findings align with Storozhenko (2019), who argues that the perception of shopping experience and products fluctuates frequently due to social networks, with Instagram often being a platform where this phenomenon is observed. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that focus on promoting the uniqueness of their product brand have a greater likelihood of utilizing viral marketing. Additionally, the trend of online shopping is steadily increasing, with more brands engaging with Instagram influencers and bloggers. As a result, it can be inferred that interactive social media platforms have opened up numerous opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises, starting with cost savings from avoiding the need to travel to physical stores.

The examination showed that Instagram consistently impacted customer buying choices and boosted sales. The results align with Pabalkar and Negi (2020) who recognized that due to the continuously evolving technology, social media platforms, especially Instagram, have become a primary shopping platform for a large portion of the country's population (youth). More and more viewers are turning to Instagram influencers, relying on them for guidance on purchasing decisions and trust due to their appeal.

The research demonstrated that individuals utilized Instagram as a means to engage with the business sector. This review aligns with Grewal et al. (2020) findings, they emphasize that businesses that provide open, helpful, and transparent messaging show care for both potential and existing customers to social media audiences. One can establish themselves as resourceful by providing information, such as tips, advice, or by responding to questions related to a specific field. The research showed that consumers typically rely on commercial content to inform their future buying choices. These findings are consistent with the findings of Pabalkar and Negi (2020) who employed an exploratory research method, leading to the creation of a formal survey. The research showed that blogs and posts impact the behavior of young individuals, posing challenges and opportunities for businesses. The researchers found that satisfied consumers utilized forums to provide feedback on their experience with the services and products. The investigation showed that Instagram marketing had prompted businesses to explore e-commerce, such as online advertising. This result aligns with Aziz et al. (2021) findings that Instagram has transitioned into e-commerce and is now a crucial tool for marketing. The use of Instagram, especially in the realm of e-commerce, has grown significantly.

Conclusions and recommendation

This research examined how social media influence the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises. According to the results of the research, the following inferences can be made. Initially, the utilization of social media greatly influences the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises by enhancing cost efficiency, customer contentment, and market achievement. Furthermore, the utilization of social media has a positive impact on the innovation and branding of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It is advised that small and medium-sized enterprises should be motivated to utilize different accessible and cost-effective social media platforms for marketing and networking in order to quickly enhance their performance and growth. Further research should investigate the potential of social media in various industries within big corporations in order to draw broad conclusions.

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